

DEVELOPMENT OF THE MANAGEMENT OF THE FIELD OF
CULTURE AND ART IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article talks about the progress of the management of the culture and art sector in Uzbekistan. The recognition of an independent Uzbekistan by the world community, the wide foreign political and foreign economic activity of our state gave great strength and confidence in the restoration of the spiritual values and opportunities of the Uzbek people, the realization of itself as a full-fledged nation in the family of other peoples. Large-scale international relations have created a favorable ground for a deeper knowledge of world culture, to enjoy universal values.

Key words: culture, art, institution, management, strategy, value, citizenship, modern, spirituality, ideology, task, government, field, direction, activity, law, system.

РАЗВИТИЕ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В ОБЛАСТИ КУЛЬТУРЫ И
ИСКУССТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается о прогрессе управления сферой культуры и искусства в Узбекистане. Признание независимого Узбекистана мировым сообществом, широкая внешнеполитическая и внешнеэкономическая деятельность нашего государства придали большие силы и уверенность в восстановлении духовных ценностей и возможностей узбекского народа, реализации себя как полноценного государства. нация в семье других народов. Масштабные международные связи создали благоприятную почву для более глубокого познания мировой культуры, приобщения к общечеловеческим ценностям.

Ключевые слова: культура, искусство, институт, менеджмент, стратегия, ценность, гражданственность, современность, духовность, идеология, задача, власть, поле, направление, деятельность, право, система.

The recognition of an independent Uzbekistan by the world community, the wide foreign political and foreign economic activity of our state gave great strength

and confidence in the restoration of the spiritual values and opportunities of the Uzbek people, the realization of itself as a full-fledged nation in the family of other peoples. Large-scale international relations have created a favorable ground for a deeper knowledge of world culture, to enjoy universal values. Independence expanded the range of knowledge of the population of our country. From the early days of independence, special attention was paid to the fact that our national culture is one of the priority factors that elevate the spiritual world of our people, serve to preserve independence. It was put on the agenda as the most important tasks to increase cultural and art institutions, libraries, museums, theaters and other places of spirituality, strengthen their material and technical base, equip them based on the requirements of the time, provide qualified specialists, radically reform the management of the culture and art sphere, and progress. From the above points, it can be concluded that culture and art in our country are gaining priority in the history of the state, society and nation. Despite the difficulties that have arisen in the main sectors of the economy of our country, the further development of the field of culture and art, the solution of strategic issues in this area, especially the correct implementation of the management system and the elimination of existing shortcomings and problems, the training of highly qualified specialist personnel, the further improvement of the material and technical base of, decrees and resolutions aimed at social protection are being adopted and implemented in quick terms. Over the past three years, about 30 decrees and resolutions on the sphere have been signed and Universal reforms are being implemented in the history of our national culture. In particular, the decree of the head of the state “on measures to further improve the management system in the field of Culture and sports”, “on the organization of activities of the Ministry of culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, “on measures to further develop and improve the field of Culture and art”, “on the organization of the fund for the development of Culture and, Among these are the decisions” on measures to further develop and improve the activities of the Uzbek State Conservatory“, ”on the organization of the activities of the Union of composers and composers of Uzbekistan“, ”on the material technical base of the Ministry of culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan “and” on measures to further develop the art of Uzbek national status“. TODAY Life is raging. In the field of culture and art, as on other fronts, the pace of changes is high, the scale of updates is wide. And the consistent reforms that are being carried out in our country are aimed at specific and strict goals.

That is, to please our people, to strengthen their trust in tomorrow, to change consciousness and thinking, to increase the feeling of immunity to the motherland – from the secrets of our priorities. So now is the time to work, showing

a new look at life, more enthusiasm. Finding a fair solution to the shortcomings and problems that are becoming obsessed with raising the living culture of the population – the presumption of the era. Further important steps are being taken in the implementation of fundamental reforms to the management of the state and society, as well as in the further improvement of the management of the field of culture and art, which is one of the main and important areas of the social sphere. The policy pursued by the head of our state – both as an economic, political and spiritual ascension-causes a greater understanding of the world and a great change in our thinking.

This is rightfully recognized by foreign political scientists. They note that Uzbekistan is at a new stage of reforms. The goals and objectives for the development of culture and art in our country are much greater. In the process of large-scale reforms in the transition to market relations, it is impossible to allow spiritual emptiness or the ability to continue to do things that come to mind. Therefore, it is not for nothing that our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in a meeting with intellectuals, compared the duties of the Minister of Culture with the Minister of Defense. Of course. The conclusion from this is that the state cannot achieve spiritual elevation without culture and art, which are considered the main basis of society, just as it cannot be solid without defense. Restoration of ancient traditions of folk oral creativity and consistent development of national values, promotion of the best examples of the creativity of Bakhshis and epics, excellent study and development of their creativity, further increase the role and importance of Bakhshi-poets in Uzbek culture and art, as well as the creation of educational and methodological literature, master Bakhshis and epics, scientists and specialists, the decision adopted by the Cabinet of Ministers in order to financially and manatively support talented young Bakhshi “on measures to further develop and improve the art of Bakhshism and epics”, the widespread promotion of folk art, a masterpiece of national singing art, embodies such genres as song, dance, music and stage performances of different peoples. Culture is the image of our people, society. The conclusion is that the level of development of our people is assessed, first of all, according to our national culture. Therefore, all officials, industry experts and employees working in cultural and art institutions should realize that they are responsible and responsible for preserving our national culture and art and bringing it to the next generations in the reforms carried out under the leadership of the head of state to create a new image of Uzbekistan.

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